

Intestinal Obstruction on a Cecal Volvulus: A Case Study

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Abstract

Cecal volvulus is a rare cause of intestinal obstruction due to an axial twist of the caecum, ascending colon and terminal ileum around the mesenteric pedicle. It is responsible for 1 to 1.5% of all the adult's intestinal obstructions. This condition generally occurs in the minority of patients who have incomplete peritoneal fixation during development, resulting in a mobile proximal colon. Diagnosis and treatment are often delayed due to the atypical and vague clinical presentation, causing a high risk of intestinal necrosis or perforation, and consequently, a high range of mortality. Hence the importance of rapid recognition of the CT-scan signs of cecal volvulus, as well as prompt surgical management. We present the case of a 39 year old woman admitted to emergency department for a cecal volvulus confirmed on a CT-scan. She underwent an emergency therapeutic laparotomy that confirmed the diagnosis.

Introduction

Cecal volvulus refers to the axial twisting of the cecum around its own mesentery, that can also involve the terminal ileum and ascending colon due to an absence of normal cecal fixation [1], resulting in a closed-loop obstruction. It represents the second most frequent type of colonic volvulus after the sigmoid variant [2]. In case of diagnosis delay, the condition can progress to cecal gangrene and perforation, resulting in acute peritonitis. Abdominal X-ray and computed tomography (CT) are the primary imaging modalities used to confirm the diagnosis. Surgical intervention remains the only definitive treatment for cecal volvulus [1].

Here we report the case of a 39-year-old female patient who underwent surgery for a cecal volvulus.

Case Report

A 39-year-old woman presented to the emergency department with a three-day history of occlusive syndrome, manifested by abdominal bloating, inability to pass gas or stool, delayed postprandial vomiting, and diffuse abdominal pain. Her medical history was notable for a gastric ulcer associated with a chronic gastritis, which had not yet been treated. Surgical

history included resection of a superficial lipoma in the epigastric area.

On physical examination, the patient was conscious, hemodynamically and respiratory stable. Abdominal examination showed asymmetrical abdominal distension, associated with tympany and tenderness localized to the right iliac fossa. The rectal examination revealed an empty rectal vault.

The initial diagnostic step consisted of the radiological evaluation using the plain abdominal radiography. It showed a markedly distended large bowel, with multiple air-fluid levels involving both the small intestine and the colon (Fig. 1), subsequent contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen revealed a significantly distended cecum (maximum diameter : 126 mm), containing a hydroaerial level, and abnormally located in the left hypochondrium. The distension was observed above a transitional level identified at the level of a right-sided spiral turn at the ileocecal junction, involving both the cecum and mesenteric fat. This configuration generated a mass effect on the pancreas, spleen, and stomach, with a significant upstream esophageal dilation measuring up to 75 mm in diameter. There was also significant thinning of the cecal wall, with areas of parietal

More Information

How to cite this article: El Wassi A, Zalarh F, Mastar H, Bouali I, Ettaoussi A, Kamal K, Majd A, Bouali M, El Bakouri A, El Hattabi K. Intestinal Obstruction on a Cecal Volvulus: A Case Study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;4(1):31-5.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).04

Keywords:

Cecal volvulus, Volvulus, Cecum, Intestinal obstruction, Laparotomy, Emergency surgery.

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pneumatosis, but no definite loss of wall enhancement (Fig. 2). A distension of the small bowel loops (measuring 46 mm in maximum diameter) was also observed. The right iliac fossa appeared empty given the abnormal positioning of the cecum in the left hypochondrium, resulting in inferior displacement of the colonic frame, as well as a collapse of the rest of the colon. No radiological evidence of intestinal ischemia or perforation was identified.

Based on these results, the diagnosis of cecal volvulus was confirmed, and the decision for urgent surgical intervention was made. The patient was promptly transferred to the operating room.

A midline incision above and below the umbilicus was performed, to access the abdominal cavity. Intraoperative exploration revealed a moderate amount of serous fluid within the peritoneal cavity and torsion of the ascending colon around its mesenteric axis, creating two spiral turns anti-clockwise forming a cecal volvulus (Fig. 3). The volvulus was complicated by multiple pre-perforative lesions (Fig. 4). The appendix appeared completely normal (Fig. 5). The stricture area was located at the right colic angle. The rest of the colon was normal. There is also a 4 cm distension of the small intestine without signs of ischemia.

Consequently, a right hemicolectomy was performed (Fig. 6).

Figure 1: Radiography of Our Patient Showing the Air-Fluid Levels in Both the Small Intestine and the Colon

Figure 2: CT-Scan of Our Patient Showing the Distended Cecum, as Well as the Spiral Turn

During the procedure, the patient developed significant hemodynamic instability, with blood pressure dropping to 70/40 mmHg and tachycardia at 134 bpm, requiring the initiation of norepinephrine. In view of this instability and the patient's overall condition, the surgical team decided to shorten the procedure and avoid the high risk of anastomotic leakage associated

with an end-to-end ileocolonic anastomosis under such circumstances. Consequently, a double-barreled ileocolostomy was performed. Restoration of intestinal continuity will be scheduled at a later date.

The results of the histopathological examination of the resected specimen revealed a non-invasive, high-grade mucinous appendiceal neoplasm, associated with

necrotic and hemorrhagic changes related to volvulus, with clear margins.

Figure 3: Intraoperative Image of Our Patient Showing the Spiral Turns Forming the Cecal Volvulus

Figure 4: Intraoperative Images of Our Patient with Pre-Perforative Colic Lesions

Figure 5: Intraoperative Image of Our Patient Showing a Macroscopically Normal Appendix (Arrow)

Figure 6: Right Hemicolectomy Specimen of Our Patient

During the postoperative follow-up, the patient developed dyspnea associated with tachycardia on postoperative day 3. A chest CT angiogram confirmed a pulmonary embolism. She was subsequently admitted to the intensive care unit, where she received oxygen therapy and curative-dose heparin. After clinical improvement and hemodynamic stabilization, the patient was discharged with a good general condition and a functional stoma. She was released under anticoagulant therapy and scheduled for follow-up in the cardiology department. and referred to the oncology department for further management.

Discussion

Cecal volvulus is a rare clinical entity and an uncommon etiology of intestinal obstruction. It accounts for approximately 1–1.5% of all cases of intestinal

obstruction and represents 20–40% of all colonic volvulus [1]. The condition typically arises in the small proportion (11–25%) of individuals with developmental failure of peritoneal fixation, which allows the proximal colon to remain mobile. Additionally, the presence of a fixed point within the abdomen—such as an adhesion, abdominal mass, or scarring from calcified lymph nodes—acts as a fulcrum for the bowel's rotation [3]. Moreover, cecal volvulus may also arise as a consequence of postoperative adhesions, chronic constipation, pregnancy, or prolonged immobility [4]. While sigmoid volvulus is common among the elderly, cecal volvulus typically occurs in younger patients, generally between 30 and 60 years of age [5].

Two mechanisms of cecal volvulus can be described :

- Torsion of the cecum around its base called the 'true' cecal volvulus, occurring through an organoaxial mechanism and generally involving torsion of the terminal ileum (90% of cases). This form carries a higher risk of necrosis because it involves the cecum, its mesentery, and its vessels
- Cecal bascule, in contrast, occurs through a mesentericoaxial mechanism (10%).

In addition, a combination of both mechanisms is also possible [6].

Typical symptoms include acute cramping, abdominal pain and distension, nausea and vomiting. Consequently, clinical examination findings may be variable and often do not contribute significantly to establishing the diagnosis. Therefore, timely diagnosis is essential, as delays may lead to catastrophic outcomes [5,7].

Laboratory findings in cecal volvulus are neither sensitive nor specific for diagnosis [7], it may reveal cases of hemoconcentration and electrolyte imbalances related to dehydration [6].

The diagnostic value of plain abdominal radiographs is limited because the findings most frequently observed, such as « coffee-bean » sign directed toward the left upper abdomen, lateral displacement of dilated small-bowel loops related to the cecum, and lack of distal colonic gas, are not specific. These features can occur in cecal obstruction as well as in many other forms of intestinal obstruction [7].

Abdominal CT is the imaging technique of choice. It can be used not only to confirm the diagnosis, but also to exclude other causes of acute obstruction [8]. It can include various scannographic signs, particularly : « coffee bean » configuration, pronounced cecal distention, « whirl sign » representing twisted cecal loops enveloping the mesenteric vessels, « ileocecal twist » where the ileum becomes incorporated into the torsion, « split-wall sign » reflecting an apparent separation of invaginated cecal walls by interposed pericolic fat, and the « X-marks-the-spot » sign representing the complete crossing of twisted bowel

loop limbs. Additionally, associated findings such as sigmoid decompression with CT evidence of a closed-loop obstruction can support rapid and confident diagnosis [7]. CT imaging may reveal features suggestive of intestinal ischemia or necrosis, including submucosal edema, reduced or absent mural enhancement, pneumatosis intestinalis, or signs of perforation such as pneumoperitoneum [1].

Water-soluble enema shows no opacification of the cecum, while the rest of the colon is of normal diameter. The progression of the contrast agent may stop forming a « bird beak » sign, confirming the diagnosis. It also unables the visualization of the distal colon in order to exclude other potential pathologies contributing to the formation of volvulus. However, because the procedure is time-consuming and carries a risk of contrast leakage in cases of gangrenous or perforated bowel, the use of this method for diagnosing acute cecal volvulus has markedly decreased [6,7].

Colonoscopy may be employed for both diagnostic evaluation and therapeutic intervention for patients without evidence of advanced ischemia. However, endoscopic detorsion often has limited success, given the high possibility of recurrence, but also the risk iatrogenic perforation [9].

Laparotomy is often necessary to confirm the diagnosis and ensure definitive surgical treatment [9].

Consequently, cecal volvulus should be considered as a surgical emergency, even in the absence of clinical or radiologic signs of severity. Right hemicolectomy with immediate anastomosis is recommended, even when colonic necrosis is not present, as it eliminates the risk of recurrence [9]. In the case of our patient, anastomosis after resection would have been performed if the patient had not presented hemodynamic instability. Consequently, a double-barreled ileocolostomy was performed.

Conservative approaches, such as cecostomy or cecopexy, are no longer advised [9]. Cecopexy alone is associated with high recurrence rates, whereas cecostomy is associated with low recurrence rates but higher rates of morbidity and mortality compared to cecopexy [7].

A laparoscopic approach is rarely used in emergency settings due to cecal distension and exposure difficulties [9].

Conclusion

Cecal volvulus develops when a mobile cecum undergoes axial torsion around its mesenteric axis. It is an uncommon but a potentially fatal cause of large bowel obstruction. Diagnosis is often delayed due to the atypical clinical presentation. Therefore the use of imaging, and most importantly the CT-scan is crucial for an early and accurate diagnosis. Management is primarily surgical. When the bowel is viable, resection

with primary anastomosis is more effective and associated with lower morbidity than other limited procedures.

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